

BIOSPACE25 (February 2025)

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Title: Optimizing ecosystem services in agricultural area: the synergy between habitat types and Nature-based Solutions.

Target 8 and 11 of the Global Biodiversity Framework aim to use ecosystem-based approaches to build resilience to climate change and restore or enhance nature's contributions to people. In the SONATA project for Serbia, we will create a detailed habitat map (EUNIS) and focus on the habitats surrounding several farmers' land to evaluate the implementation of certain nature-based solutions (NbS) based on the occurring habitat types. The goal is to discover how NbS can contribute to optimizing ecosystem services: food production, pollination potential and carbon sequestration. We will link ecosystem condition to capacity for provision of ecosystem services as we will analyze grassland condition indicators for the grasslands neighboring the farmer's fields. A spatial tool will be created that allows scenario analysis for optimizing the ecosystem services based on alternative NbS methods and their spatial distribution. The aim is to identify the optimal spatial configurations of NbS within a farmer's land to maximize the ecosystem services, according to his priority. To create the optimization models for the scenario analysis, many on-site experiments will be set up among which a pollination experiment to estimate the pollination potential and to derive yield estimates. This project will attach great value to the all-round task of 'knowledge and skill transfer' between the partners. The main goal is to implement a sustainable service of habitat mapping that can be used by the Serbian partners, and the spatial optimization tool and scenario analyses will explore the often diverging interests of different stakeholders. This will allow farmers to gain insights in the potential benefits of NbS for their businesses and it will allow policymakers to be informed on the value of NbS in targeting conservation and safeguarding the longer-term viability of agricultural activities (under climate change).

➔ *Emphasis on use of Satellite Remote Sensing data for monitoring biodiversity*